

Common model

Soils parameter:

First layer :

- Thickness : 30 cm
- Magnetic susceptibility : $50E-5$ SI
- Magnetic viscosity : $4E-5$ SI
- Electrical resistivity : 100 ohm.m (dry) (and consequently the electrical conductivity will be 10 mS/m) – 60 ohm.m (wet)
- Permittivity : 5 (dry) or 10 (wet)

Second layer :

- Magnetic susceptibility : $10 E-5$ SI
- Magnetic viscosity : $1E-5$ SI
- Electrical resistivity : 10 ohm.m (and consequently the electrical conductivity will be 100 mS/m)
- Dielectric permittivity : 25

First target: L-shaped wall

Geometry:

- Thickness: 0.5 m
- Width : 1.0 m
- Length (y direction) : 5 meter
- Length (x direction) : 2 meter
- Depth of the top : 0.3 m (so completely in the second layer)
- The longer side will start at position(x= 0,y=2.5) and ended at (x = 0, y = 7.5 meter)
- The shorter side will start at the position (x=3.5, y=2.5) and ended at (x=3.5, y=5.5)

Geophysical properties:

- Electrical resistivity : 500 ohm.m (conductivity : 5 mS/m)
- Magnetic susceptibility : $5 E-5$ SI
- Magnetic viscosity : $0.5 E-5$ SI
- Dielectric permittivity : 7
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Second target: L-shaped ditch

Geometry :

- Thickness: 0.5 m
- Width : 1.0 m
- Length (y direction) : 5 meter
- Length (x direction) : 3 meter
- Depth of the top : 0.3 m (so completely in the second layer)

- The longer side will start at position(x= 4,y=2.5) and ended at (x = 4, y = 7.5 meter)
- The shorter side will start at the position (x=3.5, y=2.5) and ended at (x=6x.5, y=5.5)

Geophysical properties :

- Electrical resistivity : 50 ohm.m (conductivity : 20 mS/m)
- Magnetic susceptibility : 100 E-5 SI
- Magnetic viscosity : 8E-5 SI
- Dielectric permittivity : 5

Third target: 3 pillares and pits

Size: 1*1 meter

Thickness: 0.5 meter

Pillar

- Pillar 1 (x=3,y=3) pillar 2 (x=3,y=5) pillar 3 (x=3,y=7)
- Top of the pillar 1 : 0.3 meter
- Top of the pillar 2: 0.5 meter
- Top of the pillar 3: 1 meter

Geophysical properties:

- Electrical resistivity : 500 ohm.m (conductivity : 5 mS/m)
- Magnetic susceptibility : 5 E-5 SI
- Magnetic viscosity : 0.5 E-5 SI
- Dielectric permittivity : 7

Pits :

- Pit 1 (x=7,y=3) – Pit 2 (x=7,y=5) – Pit 3 (x=7,y=7)
- Top of the pit 1 : 0.3 meter,
- Top of the pit 2: 0.5 meter
- Top of the pit 3: 1 meter

Geophysical properties:

- Electrical resistivity : 50 ohm.m (conductivity : 20 mS/m)
- Magnetic susceptibility : 100 E-5 SI
- Magnetic viscosity : 8E-5 SI
- Dielectric permittivity : 5

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